

SYNTHESIS OF POLYNUCLEAR HYDROCARBONS WITH FUDED *cyclopentane* RING. PART VI†

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The diene-synthesis method has been further extended to the syntheses of hydrindene derivatives including 4:7-diphenylhydrindene, two dialkyl-9:10-*cyclopentenophenanthrenes*, and a few benzo and dibenzo derivatives of *cyclopentenophenanthrene*. 1:2:3:4-Bicyclopentenophenanthrene and 3:6-dimethylphenanthrene have also been synthesised.

Diels-Alder reaction has been used for the synthesis of a few hydrindene derivatives, using Δ^1 -*cyclopentene*-1:2-dicarboxylic anhydride (I) as the dienophile component and a suitable open-chain or alicyclic diene as the second component. The adduct is obtained in the form of a dicarboxylic anhydride, which in certain cases could be decarboxylated and dehydrogenated to the corresponding aromatic hydrocarbon containing a fused *cyclopentane* ring.

4:7-Diphenylhydrindene (IV) has been synthesised starting from 1:4-diphenylbutadiene and Δ^1 -*cyclopentene*-1:2-dicarboxylic anhydride (I). These two combine when heated in xylene solution affording a mixture of the adduct (II: R=Ph) and its isomer, presumably differing in the position of the double bond. Kuhn and Wagner-Jauregg (*Ber.*, 1930, 63, 2662) also noted formation of isomeric adducts during addition of maleic anhydride to 1:4-diphenylbutadiene. When, however, 1:4-diphenylbutadiene is heated with the anhydride (I) in boiling nitrobenzene solution, a homogeneous product is formed. In the latter case the normal adduct first formed has been dehydrogenated by nitrobenzene to 8:9-dihydro-4:7-diphenylhydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic anhydride (III: R=Ph). Similar dehydrogenation of an adduct had been noted previously (Bergmann *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1942, 7, 303; Swain and Todd, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 626). The mixture of adduct (II: R=Ph) and its isomer on distillation with soda-lime under reduced pressure is simultaneously decarboxylated and dehydrogenated with the formation of 4:7-diphenylhydrindene (IV).

In a similar manner 1-phenyl-4-(*p*-tolyl)-butadiene condensed with the anhydride (I) in boiling xylene solution with the formation of a mixture of 4:7:8:9-tetrahydro-4-phenyl-7-(*p*-tolyl)-hydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic anhydride (II: R=*p*-Tol) and its isomer. This mixture

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of adducts could not be decarboxylated to the corresponding hydrocarbon by heating with soda-lime. It was found to dissociate into its components.

1 : 8-Diphenyloctatetraene on heating with two molecules of the anhydride (I) in boiling xylene solution, however, furnished a homogeneous adduct (V), formed by the addition of the two components in unimolecular proportion; but Kuhn and Wagner-Jauregg (*loc. cit.*) observed that two molecules of maleic anhydride invariably added on to one molecule of 1 : 8-diphenyloctatetraene. The adduct formation in the present case with only one molecule of the anhydride (I) may be ascribed to its comparatively low activity.

*iso*Safrol with the anhydride (I) readily formed adduct (VI), which resisted decarboxylation. A benzohydrindene derivative (VII) with an oxygen bridge has been obtained as an adduct from 1 : 3-diphenyl-5 : 6-dimethylisobenzofuran and Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1 : 2-dicarboxylic anhydride. The adduct has been found quite stable.

The synthesis of 9 : 10-cyclopentenophenanthrene was described earlier (*this Journal*, 1954, **31**, 899). We have now synthesised 2 : 7-dimethyl-9 : 10-cyclopentenophenanthrene (X : R=Me; R'=H) and 3 : 6-dimethyl-9 : 10-cyclopentenophenanthrene (X : R=H; R'=Me) by a similar procedure. The anhydride (I) readily formed adduct with 4 : 4'-dimethyl-1 : 1'-bicyclohexenyl (VIII : R=Me; R'=H). The adduct has been found to be a mixture of (IX : R=Me; R'=H) and its bond isomer. This adduct on decarboxylation furnished a product, which on selenium dehydrogenation yielded 2 : 7-dimethyl-9 : 10-cyclopentenophenanthrene (X : R=Me; R'=H). 3 : 6-Dimethyl-9 : 10-cyclopentenophenanthrene has been obtained similarly from the anhydride (I) and the diene 5 : 5'-dimethyl-1 : 1'-bicyclohexenyl (VIII : R=H; R'=Me). The latter diene has been prepared by the bimolecular reduction of 3-methylcyclohexanone and dehydration of the diol formed. The position of the methyl groups in this diene has been established by formation of its maleic anhydride adduct and decarboxylation, and dehydrogenation of the latter to 3 : 6-dimethylphenanthrene.

1:2:3:4-Bicyclopentenophenanthrene (XII) has been synthesised, starting from 1-(α -naphthyl)-cyclopentene-1 and the anhydride (I). These two combined in boiling nitrobenzene solution to form 1:2-dihydro-1:2:3:4-bicyclopentenophenanthrene-1:2-dicarboxylic anhydride (XI). Evidently dehydrogenation of the adduct took place in nitrobenzene solution. The adduct on decarboxylation with soda-lime under reduced pressure furnished the hydrocarbon (XII).

Two cyclopentenodibenzophenanthrene derivatives have also been synthesised. 9:10-cyclopenteno-3:4:5:6-dibenzo-octahydrophenanthrene-9:10-dicarboxylic anhydride (XIII: R=H) has been obtained as an adduct when 3:4:3':4'-tetrahydro-1:1'-dinaphthyl and the anhydride (I) are heated in xylene solution for long hours. In a similar manner the adduct (XIII: R=Me) has been obtained from 7:7'-dimethyl-3:4:3':4'-tetrahydro-1:1'-dinaphthyl and the anhydride (I). These two adducts could not be decarboxylated to the corresponding hydrocarbons.

We utilised earlier (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 39) cyclopentadienone derivatives as diene component in several syntheses. We have now synthesised 9:10-benzo-1:4-diphenyl-2:3-cyclopentenophenanthrene-2:3-dihydrodicarboxylic acid (XV), starting from phenecyclone and the anhydride (I). These two readily combined in boiling xylene solution with the formation of adduct (XIV). The latter loses the carbonyl bridge when heated in tetralin solution at 200° and the decarboxylated product was isolated as the dicarboxylic acid (XV). This could not be decarboxylated to the corresponding hydrocarbon.

EXPERIMENTAL

4:7:8:9-Tetrahydro-4:7-diphenylhydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic Anhydride (II: R=Ph).—1:4-Diphenylbutadiene (10g.) and the anhydride of Δ^1 -cyclopentene-1:2-dicarboxylic acid (7g.) in dry xylene (25 c.c.) were refluxed for 5 hours at 150-55°, and then kept overnight at the room temperature. The solvent was removed by steam distillation and the residual solid was twice crystallised from benzene to furnish silky needles of the mixed isomers. It softens at 205° and clearly melts at 212°. (Found: C, 79.8; H, 5.8. $C_{23}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 80.0; H, 5.8%).

8:9-Dihydro-4:7-diphenylhydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic Anhydride (III: R=Ph).—A mixture of 1:4-diphenylbutadiene (6g.) and the anhydride (I) (4g.) was gently boiled in nitrobenzene (25 c.c.) solution for 3 hours, and then left overnight at room temperature. Nitrobenzene was removed by steam distillation. The solid residue crystallised from benzene in fine needles, m.p. 217-18°, yield 5.6 g. (Found: C, 80.5; H, 5.3. $C_{23}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 80.7; H, 5.26%).

4:7-Diphenylhydrindene (IV).—The adduct (II: R=Ph) (6g.) and soda-lime (6g.) were thoroughly mixed and heated in a test tube under reduced pressure. The liquid distillate obtained was taken in ether, dried, and distilled under reduced pressure. The liquid distillate had a pinkish fluorescence and solidified on cooling. It was crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 108°, yield 2 g. (Found: C, 92.95; H, 6.7. $C_{21}H_{18}$ requires C, 93.3; H, 6.7%).

4:7:8:9-Tetrahydro-4-phenyl-7-(*p*-tolyl)-hydrindene-8:9-dicarboxylic Anhydride (II: R=*p*-Tol).—1-Phenyl-4-(*p*-tolyl)-butadiene (10g.) and the relevant anhydride (8g.) were heated in xylene solution and worked up as in the former case. The adduct crystallised from benzene, m.p. 188-90°, yield 8 g. (Found: C, 80.40; H, 6.4. $C_{21}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 80.44; H, 6.14%).

The adduct dissociated into its components when heated with soda-lime under reduced pressure.

Formation of the Adduct (V).—1 : 8-Diphenyloctatetraene (7g.) and the anhydride (I) (7g.) were refluxed in xylene solution for 10 hours till the yellow colour of the diene almost faded away. The adduct was worked up as in other cases. It crystallised from xylene, m.p. 206°, yield 3.5g. (Found: C, 81.9; H, 6.4. $C_{27}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 81.86; H, 6.06%). The adduct (V) decomposed during decarboxylation.

7-Methyl-(2': 3'-dioxymethylene-4 : 5-benzo)-6 : 7 : 8 : 9-tetrahydrohydrindene-8 : 9-dicarboxylic Anhydride (VI).—*iso*Safrol (10g.) and the anhydride (I) (8g.) were heated in xylene solution and the adduct separated as in other cases. It was crystallised first from acetic anhydride and then from benzene, m.p. 172°, yield 4 g. (Found: C, 68.0; H, 4.95. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 68.0; H, 5.3%). The adduct decomposed on heating with soda-lime.

4 : 7-Diphenyl-4 : 7-endoxo-(2': 3'-dimethyl-5 : 6-benzo)-4 : 7 : 8 : 9-tetrahydrohydrindene-8 : 9-dicarboxylic Anhydride (VII).—1 : 3-Diphenyl-5 : 6-dimethylisobenzofuran (2g.) (Adams and Marvin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 57) and the anhydride (I) (1.5g.) in xylene (10 c.c.) were gently boiled for 3 hours. The adduct separated on cooling and was crystallised from benzene in colorless cubes, m.p. 286°. (Found: C, 79.85; H, 5.41. $C_{26}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 79.81; H, 5.5%).

9 : 10-cyclopenteno-2 : 7-dimethyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4 : 5 : 6 : 7 : 8 : 9 : 10 : 11 : 14-dodecahydrophenanthrene-9-10-dicarboxylic Anhydride (IX: R=Me; R'=H).—4 : 4'-Dimethyl-1 : 1'-bicyclohexenyl (VIII: R=Me; R'=H) (15g.) and the anhydride (I) (10g.) in dry xylene were heated for 9 hours and worked up as before. The adduct crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 115°, sintering earlier; yield 8g. (Found: C, 77.2; H, 8.69. $C_{21}H_{26}O_3$ requires C, 76.82; H, 8.53%).

2 : 7-Dimethyl-9 : 10-cyclopentenophenanthrene (X: R=Me; R'=H).—The foregoing adduct (6 g.) mixed with soda-lime (8g.) was heated under reduced pressure. The liquid distillate was taken in ether, dried with calcium chloride, and the solvent removed. The residual liquid (2.5g.) was mixed with selenium (7g.) and heated at 300-20° for 24-hours, extracted with ether, the solvent removed, and the residue distilled over sodium under reduced pressure. The first fraction of the distillate is a liquid and the second fraction, a solid (1g.). The solid fraction was converted into picrate, the hydrocarbon regenerated from it and crystallised from ethanol in fine needles, m.p. 163°. (Found: C, 92.7; H, 7.48. $C_{18}H_{18}$ requires C, 92.68; H, 7.31%).

The *picrate* was obtained from ethanolic solution in orange needles, m.p. 152°. (Found: C, 62.85; H, 4.5. $C_{25}H_{21}O_7N_3$ requires C, 63.15; H, 4.42%). The *trinitrobenzene complex* had m.p. 172°. (Found: C, 65.1; H, 4.7. $C_{25}H_{21}O_9N_3$ requires C, 65.35; H, 4.57%).

5 : 5'-Dimethyl-1 : 1'-bicyclohexenyl.—3-Methylcyclohexanone was reduced with aluminium amalgam in dry benzene in the usual manner. The crude diol was dehydrated by anhydrous potassium bisulphate at 160-80°. The diene distilled at 129-30°/12 mm. (Found: C, 88.23; H, 11.36. $C_{14}H_{22}$ requires C, 88.42; H, 11.57%).

Synthesis of 3 : 6-Dimethylphenanthrene.—5 : 5'-Dimethyl-1 : 1'-bicyclohexenyl (7g.) was heated with maleic anhydride (10g.) in dry xylene (12 c.c.) at 140-50° for 5 hours. After removal of the xylene the adduct was obtained as a solid mass. The potassium salt of the adduct was prepared with caustic potash, and the dry salt was mixed with soda-lime and heated under reduced pressure when a liquid distillate (1g.) was obtained. This was dried over sodium sulphate and then heated with 10% Pd-C (0.1g.) at 300-20° for 12 hours. The dehydrogenated product was extracted with benzene, the solvent removed, and the residual hydrocarbon was purified through its *picrate*. The hydrocarbon had m.p. 140°. (Found: C, 93.0; H, 6.9. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{14}$: C, 93.2;

H, 6.79%). The picrate obtained from ethanolic solution in orange needles had m.p. 172°. Haworth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 458) records m.p. of 3 : 6-dimethylphenanthrene and its picrate as 141° and 171° respectively.

~~5 : 6-Dimethyl-9 : 10-cyclopentenophenanthrene~~ (X : R=H; R'=Me).—5 : 5'-Dimethyl-1 : 1'-bicyclohexenyl (IX : R=H; R'=Me) (8g.) and the anhydride (I) (5g.) in dry xylene were heated for 8 hours and worked up as before. The adduct could not be obtained in an analytically pure form. The dry adduct was mixed with soda-lime and heated under reduced pressure. The liquid distillate (2g.) was dried and heated with 10% Pd-C (0.2g.) at 300-20° for 12 hours. The dehydrogenated product was extracted with ether and distilled to afford a solid fraction (1.2g.). This was converted into the picrate and the regenerated hydrocarbon was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 175°. (Found : C, 92.3; H, 7.7. $C_{19}H_{18}$ requires C, 92.68; H, 7.31%.)

The picrate was obtained as deep red needles, sparingly soluble in ethanol, m.p. 185°. (Found : C, 59.45; H, 4.51. $C_{25}H_{21}O_4N_3$ requires C, 63.15; H, 4.4%). The trinitrobenzene complex was obtained from ethanolic solution in orange needles, m.p. 220°. (Found : C, 65.2; H, 4.7. $C_{25}H_{21}O_4N_3$ requires C, 65.35; H, 4.57%.)

1 : 2-Dihydro-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-bicyclopentenophenanthrene-1 : 2-dicarboxylic Anhydride (XI).—1-(α -Naphthyl)-cyclopentene-1 (Bachmann and Kloetzl, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2204) (5g.) and the anhydride (I) (4g.) in nitrobenzene (25 c.c.) were refluxed gently for 2 hours. The solvent was removed and the residue crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 164-65°, yield 2g. (Found : C, 79.63; H, 5.37. $C_{22}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 80.0; H, 5.45%.)

1 : 2 : 3 : 4-Bicyclopentenophenanthrene (XII).—The adduct (XI, 2g.) was mixed with soda-lime and heated at 250°-300°/10 mm, when a distillate (1.2g.) was obtained. This readily solidified and crystallised from ethanol in colorless flakes, m.p. 137-38°. (Found : C, 92.65; H, 7.2. $C_{20}H_{18}$ requires C, 93.02; H, 6.97%.)

9 : 10-cyclopenteno-3 : 4 : 5 : 6-dibenzo-octahydrophenanthrene-9 : 10-dicarboxylic Anhydride (XIII : R=H).—3 : 4 : 3' : 4'-Tetrahydro-1 : 1'-dinaphthyl (10g.) (Weidlich, *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1203), and the anhydride (I) (8g.) in xylene (30 c.c.) were refluxed for 18 hours. The solvent was removed and the adduct was crystallised from acetic anhydride, m.p. 262°, yield 5g. (Found : C, 81.7; H, 5.8. $C_{27}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 81.8; H, 6.0%.)

7 : 7'-Dimethyl-3 : 4 : 3' : 4'-tetrahydro-1 : 1'-dinaphthyl.—7-Methyltetralin-1-one was reduced with aluminium amalgam in dry benzene-ethanol medium according to the usual procedure, and the diol obtained was dehydrated by heating with glacial acetic acid. The diene thus formed was crystallised from acetic acid as a colorless substance, m.p. 110°. (Found : C, 92.0; H, 7.9. $C_{22}H_{22}$ requires C, 92.3; H, 7.69%.)

9 : 10-cyclopenteno-3 : 4 : 5 : 6-bis-(2'-methylbenzo)-octahydrophenanthrene-9 : 10-dicarboxylic Anhydride (XIII : R=Me).—7 : 7'-Dimethyl-3 : 4 : 3' : 4'-tetrahydro-1 : 1'-dinaphthyl (5g.) and the anhydride (I) in xylene (20 c.c.) were refluxed for 18 hours and worked up as in the former case. The adduct was crystallised from toluene, m.p. 245°, yield 2.2g. (Found : C, 81.7; H, 6.2. $C_{29}H_{28}O_3$ requires C, 82.07; H, 6.6%.)

9 : 10-Benzo-1 : 4-diphenyl-1 : 4-endocarbonyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydro-2 : 3-cyclopentenophenanthrene-2 : 3-dicarboxylic Anhydride (XIV).—Phenecyclone (8g.) and the anhydride (I) (6g.) in xylene (30 c.c.) were heated at 150° for 3 hours. No carbon monoxide was evolved during condensation. On cooling colorless crystals of the adduct separated. This was collected, washed with

benzene and crystallised from acetic anhydride in fine needles, m.p. 285° (decomp.), yield 8g. (Found: C, 83.21; H, 4.67. $C_{30}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 83.07; H, 4.61%).

9:10-*Benzo-1:4-diphenyl-2:3-cyclopentenophenanthrene-2:3-dihydrodicarboxylic Acid* (XV). The foregoing adduct (XIV) (2g.) was heated in tetralin (20 c.c.) at 200° until the evolution of carbon monoxide had ceased (about 3 hours). The solvent was removed by steam distillation and the residual solid was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 303° (decomp.). (Found: C, 82.3; H, 4.8. $C_{25}H_{28}O_4$ requires C, 82.34; H, 5.09%).

No attempt was made to separate isomers formed in the Diels-Alder reaction.

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